

BROMINATION OF ACETYLURETHANE AND ACETYL-SUBSTITUTED UREAS

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Acetyl-phenyl, -*o*-tolyl, -*m*-tolyl, -*p*-tolyl, - α -naphthyl, - β -naphthyl, -*p*-xylyl, -*o*-anisyl, -*p*-phenetyl and -*m*-phenetyl carbamides and acetylurethane have been brominated and the constitution of bromo derivatives so obtained has been established by synthesis.

Extensive work has been done on halogenation and replacement of halogens by hydrogen in compounds containing—CO—CH₂—CO—grouping (Whiteley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 710 ; 1925, 748 ; Naik *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 355, 365, 431). Bromination of compounds containing —CO—NH—CO— grouping has been studied in this paper on acetyl-phenyl-*o*-tolyl, -*m*-tolyl, -*p*-tolyl, α -naphthyl, β -naphthyl, -*p*-xylyl, -*o*-anisyl, -*p*-phenetyl and -*m*-phenetyl carbamides and acetylurethane and it has been found that bromine enters only the nucleus in phenyl-substituted ureas and only the methyl group in acetylurethane. The constitution of the halogen derivatives so obtained has been established by synthesising the same compounds from the corresponding amino derivatives and acetylurethane.

EXPERIMENTAL

Substitued Carbamides.—The acetyl derivatives of substituted carbamides were obtained from acetylurea and amino compounds by heating them on an oil-bath at 160° with an air condenser when ammonia was evolved and the reaction completed in about 3 hours. The products were treated with water, dried and crystallised from alcohol or ethyl acetate. The compounds so obtained are identical with those prepared from acetylurethane and the corresponding amino compounds. Acetyl-*m*-phenetylcarbamide, m.p. 162-65°. (Found : N, 12.2. C₁₁H₁₄O₃ N₂ requires N, 12.61 per cent).

Acetyl-*o*-phenetylcarbamide, m.p. 212-13°.

Acetyl-*o*-anisylcarbamide, m.p. 194-95°.

Acetyl-*p*-xylylcarbamide, m.p. 172-73°.

On hydrolysis with potassium hydroxide solution on a water-bath for half an hour, acetyl group was removed and the free substituted carbamides obtained and crystallised from aqueous alcohol.

o-Phenetylcarbamide, m.p. 135-36°. (Found : N, 15.3. C₉H₁₂O₂N₂ requires N, 15.55 per cent).

p-Anisylcarbamide, m.p. 162-63°. (Found : N, 16.38. C₈H₁₀O₂N₂ requires N, 16.86 per cent).

p-(1 : 4 : 5)-Xylylcarbamide, m.p. 209-10°, resolidifying and decomposing rapidly above 275°. (Found : N, 16.5. C₉H₁₂ON₂ requires N, 17.01 per cent).

Bromo Derivatives.—The substituted carbamide (1 g.) was suspended in carbon tetrachloride in a flask and bromine in excess was added slowly. After the addition was over, the contents were refluxed for about 3 hours, cooled, filtered, washed with benzene and crystallised from alcohol. They are white crystalline solids, insoluble in water, soluble in hot alcohol, and sparingly in hot benzene.

Acetyl-4-bromophenetylcarbamide, m.p. 218-19°. (Found : N, 11.11 ; Br, 31.05. C₉H₉O₂N₂Br requires N, 10.9 ; Br, 31.12 per cent).

Acetyl-5-bromotolylcarbamide, m.p. 226-28°. (Found : N, 10.39 ; Br, 28.93. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2N_2Br$ requires N, 10.33 ; Br, 29.52 per cent).

Acetyl-4 : 6-dibromo-*m*-tolylcarbamide, m.p. 215-17°. (Found : N, 8.45 ; Br, 45.5. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2Br_2$ requires N, 8.0 ; Br, 45.7 per cent).

Acetyl-3-bromo-*p*-tolylcarbamide, m.p. 226-28°. (Found : N, 10.26 ; Br, 28.0. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2N_2Br$ requires N, 10.33 ; Br, 29.5 per cent).

Acetyl-4-bromo- α -naphthylcarbamide, blackening at 235-40° and melting at 258-60°. (Found : N, 9.07 ; Br, 27.0. $C_{13}H_{11}O_2N_2Br$ requires N, 9.16 ; Br, 26.05 per cent).

Acetyl-1-bromo- β -naphthylcarbamide, m.p. 226-28°. (Found : N, 9.21 ; Br, 25.3. $C_{13}H_{11}O_2N_2Br$ requires N, 9.17 ; Br, 26.05 per cent).

Acetyl-2-bromo-(1 : 4 : 5)-xylylcarbamide, m.p. 205-206°. (Found : N, 10.9 ; Br, 26.6. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_2Br$ requires N, 9.82 ; Br, 28.0 per cent).

Acetyl-4-bromo-*o*-anisylcarbamide, m.p. 232-34°. (Found : N, 9.48 ; Br, 28.7. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3N_2Br$ requires N, 9.68 ; Br, 28.7 per cent).

Acetyl-4-bromo-*o*-phenetylcarbamide, m.p. 236-38°. (Found : N, 9.28 ; Br, 27.5. $C_{11}H_{14}O_3N_2Br$ requires N, 9.30 ; Br, 26.6 per cent).

Acetyl-dibromo-*m*-phenetylcarbamide, m.p. 236-38°. (Found : N, 9.28 ; Br, 41.28. $C_{11}H_{12}O_3N_2Br_2$ requires N, 7.36 ; Br, 42.1 per cent).

Bromoacetylurethane, m.p. 120-21°. (Found : N, 6.45 ; Br, 37.17. $C_5H_9O_3NBr$ requires N, 6.65 ; Br, 38.09 per cent). In the case of this compound, no heating is required. Mere keeping overnight gives the product on evaporation of the solvent.

All these bromo compounds have also been synthesised from acetylurethane and the corresponding bromo-amino compounds and thus their constitution established.

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